

Using near-surface atmospheric measurements as a proxy for quantifying field-scale soil gas flux

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ABSTRACT: We present a new method for deriving surface soil gas flux at the field scale, which is less field-work intensive than traditional chamber techniques and less expensive than those derived from airborne or space surveys. The technique uses aspects of chamber and micrometeorological methods combined with a mobile platform and GPS to rapidly derive soil gas fluxes at the field-scale. There are several assumptions in using this method, which will be most accurate under stable atmospheric conditions with little horizontal wind flow. Results show that soil gas fluxes, when averaged across a field site, are highly comparable between the method presented and traditional chamber acquisition techniques. Atmospheric dilution is found to reduce the range of flux values under the open field-scale method, when compared to chamber derived results. Under ideal atmospheric conditions it may be possible to use the presented method to derive soil gas flux at an individual point, however this requires further investigation. The new method for deriving soil-atmosphere gas exchange at the field-scale could be useful for a number of applications including quantification of CCS leakage, diffuse degassing in volcanic and geothermal areas and greenhouse-gas emissions.

INTRODUCTION

The study of soil-atmosphere gas exchange has become more prominent over the past couple of decades. Objectives for these studies are wide-ranging, for example: the study of volcanic degassing^[1,2]; quantification of carbon budgets^[3,4]; greenhouse gas (GHG) emission studies^[5]; and identifying potential leakage from Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) and Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) sites^[6-8]. Soil gas emissions are directly measured at points or spots using chamber techniques^[9] or over restricted areas through micrometeorological methods^[10]. At regional and national scales, airborne and space measurements are used to derive soil gas emissions using empirical and process-oriented models for post-processing. These regional scale methods lack detail required for field-scale studies (10^1 to 10^3 m²) and may be prohibitively expensive⁵. There is currently a lack of practical methods for quantifying soil gas flux rates at field-scales, which are highly relevant to leakage and degassing studies. Feitz et al.^[11] provide a comparison of many of these techniques under a controlled gas release.

Closed loop flux chamber-based analyses utilize an open-bottomed chamber with a known footprint and volume placed on the soil surface, allowing gases emitted by the soil to accumulate within the chamber headspace. From analysis of the gas mixing ratios within the chamber over time, the flux of gas from the soil can be derived for that small spot of the land surface. In contrast, an open loop technique passes air through the sample chamber just once at a known flow rate, until a steady-state concentration is observed, from which a flux rate is derived. Both techniques require measurements at a large number of points to estimate field-scale fluxes via interpolation, with the caveats that sample density is sufficient to represent site spatial variability and that flux is static with respect to time during the measurement period. Micrometeorological methods use eddy covariance (EC) techniques to derive soil gas flux. A three-di-

43 dimensional sonic anemometer is coupled to a gas analyser attached to a tower or mast, allowing meas-
44 urements that incorporate areas of up to several square kilometers under the right atmospheric and
45 terrain conditions^[12]. Continuous EC measurements over a period of time allow soil gas fluxes for a par-
46 ticular parcel of land to be derived from absolute gas concentrations, temperature, and vertical and hor-
47 izontal wind flows. To ensure that the path from soil surface up to the instrument sensors is correct, the
48 technique is most suited to sites with low turbulence properties associated with short vegetation and level
49 ground.

50

51 The use of chambers to represent soil-gas fluxes at field-scale is often highly time-intensive and prone
52 to interpolation-related uncertainty^[13], particularly for sites with heterogeneous soils or geology. Micro-
53 meteorological methods can also be difficult to implement at the field-scale as they are reliant on wind
54 direction and non-turbulent atmospheric conditions between the ground-surface and the sensors.

55

56 The objective of this paper is present a new method that uses aspects of chamber and micrometeor-
57 ological methods combined with a mobile platform and GPS to rapidly derive soil gas fluxes at the field-
58 scale. We assess this method against traditional chamber techniques for field locations within the UK
59 and Italy, and discuss the explicit and implicit assumptions inherent in the presented techniques.

60

61 MATERIALS AND METHODS

62 Development of a new field-scale soil CO₂ flux quantification method was focused on creating a
63 mobile tool that could easily and quickly make measurements around a field site without the need for
64 stopping at individual locations. Here we describe the theoretical aspects, assumptions made and com-
65 ponents used to undertake the measurements.

66

67 **Experimental theory.** As we approach the ground surface, frictional drag reduces horizontal wind
68 speed to near-zero. The depth of this frictional influence depends on the roughness of the surface^[14]. By
69 assuming that there is no horizontal wind flow close to the surface, we can discretize the near-surface
70 atmosphere into non-interacting boxes of air, each with a base fixed on the ground surface, and treat
71 each of these as a type of 'open' dynamic flux chamber. Open chambers use two openings, an inlet that
72 draws ambient air and an outlet, to generate a continuous gas flow. The gas flux is calculated by the
73 concentration difference between these two ends under a known flow rate through the system^[15]. Simi-
74 larly, if we know the concentration of a particular gas within our air boxes, the atmospheric background
75 concentration and the vertical flow rate of air up through the box, we can calculate soil gas flux in a similar
76 way. In other words, we calculate the amount of extra gas required to maintain a particular stable con-
77 centration near the surface. This may be derived from the Ideal Gas Law:

78

$$79 \quad Flux = M_m \left(\frac{PVw}{RT} \right) \quad [Eqn. 1]$$

80

$$81 \quad V = \frac{(Obs-Back)}{10^6} \quad [Eqn. 2]$$

82

83 Where flux (g.m⁻².s⁻¹) is calculated using: the atmospheric pressure, P (Pa); the ideal gas constant,
84 R (8.31446 m³.Pa.K⁻¹.mol⁻¹); temperature, T (K); the molar mass of the gas being sampled, M_m , (g.mol⁻¹);
85 the vertical wind speed, w (m.s⁻¹); and v (-), the volume of gas (m³) occupied by the difference in
86 concentration between observed, Obs (ppm_v) and background, $Back$ (ppm_v) per m³ air.

87

88 The physical basis for this calculation is best described using a thought experiment. Suppose we
89 have a box of air at the ground surface with a known, uniform gas concentration. As we know the volume
90 of the box and the gas concentration, we know the weight of that gas within that box from the ideal gas
91 law. Assuming the box is fully mixed, if we remove a known volume of gas from the top of the box, we
92 can calculate the weight of gas removed for a given area of land per time-step. If we replace the displaced

93 volume with background air, there will be a difference in the gas weight for the box from the original
94 weight (unless background and observed concentrations are equal). This difference equates to the gas
95 either added or removed at the soil surface as a weight for a given area of land per time-step, i.e., a soil
96 gas flux.

97
98 **Assumptions.** There are several implicit and explicit assumptions in the experimental theory pre-
99 sented for deriving field-scale soil gas fluxes. No horizontal wind flow at the measurement height is a
100 major assumption and may in practice not hold true under certain conditions, particularly under high
101 winds or on very smooth (aerodynamically) land surfaces. This can be tested in the field by measuring
102 horizontal wind flow at or near to measurement height, which itself is related to the roughness length of
103 the surface and meteorological conditions. Without horizontal wind flow, there are no turbulent conditions
104 to create the vertical components of wind flow, however, even under moderately convective conditions,
105 the vertical wind field is directly coupled to the temperature field through buoyant forces^[16]. It is also
106 assumed that a measurement point represents the entire box of air and that the air is fully mixed. As the
107 experimental theory is scalable, the size of the box can be reduced to near-zero and, therefore, the
108 assumption holds true. How well that measurement represents surrounding areas when interpolation is
109 applied in post-processing is unknown. The same issue is faced by traditional chamber methods, how-
110 ever the described open field-scale method results in a much higher density of measurements and thus
111 a comparatively reduced uncertainty. Air is assumed to be non-compressible and at a uniform tempera-
112 ture and density. The former is a standard assumption in atmospheric sciences and would require com-
113 plex adjustments to calculate, however, given the scalability, the impact of compressibility differences
114 would be minimal at a near-zero box volume. Temperature and pressure differences are accounted for
115 in the calculation of gas weights using the Ideal Gas law. Finally, we assume that replacement air comes
116 from either background atmospheric or the soil surface. In reality, there will be some replacement from
117 the surrounding air, which isn't necessarily at background. The greatest impact to this assumption comes
118 under atmospheric conditions that create high vertical wind speeds and, therefore, are likely to 'draw' air
119 from the surrounding area, such as when the land surface is much warmer than the surrounding atmos-
120 phere. The impact of air-box interaction, in comparison to chamber methods, should result in a smoother,
121 less peaky dataset.

122
123 **Field measurements.** To gather the field-scale flux data, several instruments were mounted on a
124 light-weight metal handcart which was pulled around various field sites. To measure gas concentrations
125 at the required short time intervals, we used either open path lasers or a gas analyser to measure CO₂
126 at 1Hz. These were mounted on the handcart and were sampling at a height of 10 cm from the ground
127 surface. Vertical wind flow was measured at 10 Hz using a tri-axis sonic anemometer mounted either
128 with the gas analysers or at a fixed point in the field. Finally, a global positioning system (GPS) receiver
129 was added to the cart to provide positional data for the gas and flow measurements. For each of the field
130 sites, the cart was pushed at a slow walking pace (~2 km/h) in a grid pattern. As the field data is being
131 used for multiple research purposes (for example, leakage detection), the cart was sometimes returned
132 to points with high gas concentrations to map the area in greater detail. For comparison, traditional closed
133 loop chamber methods were used to measure soil CO₂ flux on a regular grid, where appropriate, for
134 each of the field sites. For practical purposes, grid spacing for the chamber measurements was deter-
135 mined by the size of the field and the time available to take samples. Where measurements with the flux
136 chambers and the cart are not aligned, the cart measurements are interpolated.

137

138 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

139 Results are presented for field locations near Ailano, Italy and Sutton Bonington, UK. For the former
140 flux-chamber results were obtained at 80 points and for the latter at 32 points. As data from these sites
141 may be sensitive, exact locations are not given. Figure 1 shows CO₂ flux data (g.m⁻².d⁻¹, note the differ-
142 ence in temporal units from the flux equation presented in the methods section) from a single field at the
143 Ailano site, with fluxes from the chamber method plotted on top of the interpolated field-scale flux distri-
144 bution. A visual comparison shows that the open field-scale method produces values that are of a similar

145 order of magnitude to those obtained by chamber methods, although there are clear differences at indi-
146 vidual observation locations.

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148

149 **Figure 1.** CO₂ flux (g.m⁻².d⁻¹) measured using a closed loop chamber technique (circles) and that derived
150 using the open field-scale method (interpolated underlying plot), for one of the field sites in Ailano, Italy.

151 To quantitatively compare open field-scale and closed loop chamber methods at the larger scale we
152 have de-localised the datasets and derived a set of summary statistics. The difference in mean CO₂ flux
153 values between the techniques is 0.5 g m⁻² d⁻¹ for Ailano and 2.4 g m⁻² d⁻¹ for Sutton Bonington. Figure 2
154 shows box and whisker plots representing the rest of the summary statistics for both sites. At both sites,
155 the median (50% percentile) is highly comparable for both techniques, while the open field-scale method
156 exhibits less range between the 25% and 75% percentiles. Regression analysis (Fig. 3) shows the devi-
157 ation from a 1:1 relationship between the point and mobile flux techniques. The correlation of determina-
158 tion (r^2) between the techniques is 0.29 for Ailano and 0.03 for Sutton Bonington.

159

160 The results show that the average (mean and median) CO₂ flux obtained using the chamber tech-
161 nique and those derived from the open field-scale method presented in this study are highly comparable
162 at field-study scales. The range (absolute and between quartiles) of CO₂ flux is smaller in the latter
163 dataset, which, as discussed in the assumptions section, is likely due to atmospheric dilution.

164

165 **Figure 2.** Box and whisker plots comparing CO₂ flux measured using the traditional chamber technique
 166 to those derived from the field method for Ailano, Italy (blue) and Sutton Bonington, UK (green); note the
 167 much lower values at the latter. The boxes represent the 25% (bottom) and 75% (top) quartiles, and the
 168 central line the median. The whiskers extend to 1.5 times the inter-quartile range and outliers as individ-
 169 ual points.

170

171 **Figure 3.** CO₂ flux comparison of chamber vs open field-scale technique for the measurement sites
 172 in Ailano, Italy (blue) and Sutton Bonington, UK (green).

173 At individual measurement locations there is the potential for correlation between the chamber and
 174 open field-scale derived techniques, as shown at the Ailano site. However, this was not apparent in the
 175 data collected for Sutton Bonington. This could be due to atmospheric conditions or that the observed
 176 flux values were much smaller at the UK site.

177

178 The method presented for deriving surface soil gas flux at the field scale is less field-work intensive
 179 than traditional chamber techniques and cheaper than those derived from airborne or space surveys.
 180 The use of chamber and micrometeorological methods together with a mobile platform and GPS allow
 181 soil gas fluxes to be rapidly estimated at the field-scale. Due to several assumptions, the most accurate
 182 results are expected under stable atmospheric conditions, with little horizontal wind flow. When derived
 183 soil gas fluxes are averaged at the field scale, they are highly comparable to results obtained using
 184 traditional chamber techniques. As expected, atmospheric dilution leads to a reduced range of flux values
 185 under the open field-scale method. Under ideal atmospheric conditions it may be possible to use the
 186 method presented to derive soil gas flux at an individual point, however this requires further investigation.
 187 The presented method of deriving soil-atmosphere gas exchange at the field-scale could be useful for a
 188 number of applications including leakage, degassing and greenhouse-gas emission studies.

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209

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